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The slow transition to solar, wind and other non-hydro renewables in Africa – Responding to and building on a critique by Kincer, Moss and Thurber (2021)

Abstract Academic studies, IRENA and the IEA have produced prominent yet largely assumption-driven projections that non-hydro renewable generation in Africa’s power sector will leapfrog to 25% - 40% in 2030. In response, our paper in *Nature Energy* (Alova, Trotter and Money (2021)) proposed a data-driven machine learning-based approach to predicting generation capacity. Using the most comprehensive database on generation assets in Africa, it predicts the non-hydro renewables generation share to be below 10% in 2030 in Africa. This renders the aforementioned leapfrogging scenarios unlikely unless a decarbonisation shock occurs in the pipeline. In this issue, Kincer, Moss and Thurber (2021) criticise two aspects of our paper, one relating to an alleged significant overestimation of coal capacity, the other to an alleged analytical integration of African countries. They go on to make a third claim, namely that our paper calls for blanked bans on fossil fuel finance in Africa. Kincer et al.’s critique and efforts, and the opportunity to engage in this debate, are greatly appreciated. Indeed, the recent announcements by the G7 and China to stop overseas coal finance are likely to constitute a shock for coal capacity in Africa akin to those we discuss in our study. Yet this paper presents and reiterates evidence which renders the arguments behind all three of Kincer et al.’s points invalid. Critically however, this paper builds on the significant common ground with Kincer et al. and suggests a way forward that incorporates Kincer et al.’s crucial notion of context-specificity, as well as their important push to let the goal to achieve sustainable development drive energy decision making.

Introduction

The African power sector is at a crossroads. Africa’s electricity demand is set to greatly increase in the coming decades (Ouedraogo, 2017b), driven by the region’s projected economic and population dynamics (United Nations, 2019). Existing energy planning studies estimate Africa’s electricity demand in 2030 to be between 1,600 – 2,150 TWh in 2030 (International Energy Agency, 2019; International Renewable Energy Agency, 2015; Ouedraogo, 2017a; Panos et al., 2015; Taliotis et al., 2016; P.A. Trotter et al., 2018; van der Zwaan et al., 2018), a more than twofold increase compared to 2018. At the same time, in 2018, roughly 80% of Africa’s electricity was generated using fossil fuels (International Energy Agency, 2019). Coal made up roughly 30% of total generation, natural gas accounted for roughly 41% and oil contributed roughly 9%. By contrast, non-hydro renewables, i.e. all solar, wind, geothermal, biomass and marine sources combined, accounted for just over 3% of generation (International Energy Agency, 2019). Yet most existing African energy planning

studies in the academic and grey literature feature scenarios that predict between 700% and 1,200% higher solar and wind-based generation shares in Africa in 2030 compared to 2018 (International Energy Agency, 2019; International Renewable Energy Agency, 2015; Ouedraogo, 2017a; Panos et al., 2015; Taliotis et al., 2016; P.A. Trotter et al., 2018; van der Zwaan et al., 2018), fuelling increasingly prominent narratives of leapfrogging to clean energy technologies in Africa. For instance, the IEA's "Africa case" scenario in its 2019 Africa Energy Outlook report foresees a 25% share of non-hydro renewables (International Energy Agency, 2019), while IRENA's "RE-oriented" scenario yields a non-hydro renewables share of 30% – 39% in 2030 (International Renewable Energy Agency, 2015).

These scenarios, however, are based on a wide-ranging set of assumptions which tend to neglect information on existing power plant pipelines. Addressing this issue, our study, published earlier this year in *Nature Energy*, develops and applies a data-driven, machine learning-based approach to predicting electricity generation capacity in Africa in 2030 (Alova et al., 2021). It uses the most comprehensive asset-level dataset of power plants in Africa, featuring approximately 6,500 entries of operating, failed and planned projects. The main finding from this study is that while fossil fuel generation is predicted to account for two-thirds of generation in 2030 in Africa, the non-hydro renewables share of generation is predicted to not exceed 10% in 2030. This finding renders rapid leapfrogging scenarios for the African continent unlikely unless a decarbonisation shock occurs in the pipeline occurs, where large shares of fossil fuel plants are replaced with non-hydro renewables (Alova et al., 2021).

In this present issue, Kincer et al. argue that "Africa is not on the cusp of a coal boom", and go on to critique a study by the US Energy Information Agency (EIA) as well as our study for their respective results¹. Kincer et al.'s efforts to critique our paper, as well as this Symposium in general, are greatly appreciated, as an on-going debate of the important issues associated with the theme of this Symposium is critical. This paper responds to and engages with Kincer et al. Their critique entails two points, namely (1) that our paper makes "opaque projections ... for coal-fired capacity growth", and (2) that our "analysis treats Africa as one unified entity". Kincer et al. go on to say that, (3), we "call for a continent-wide ban on development finance for all fossil fuels". This paper presents and reiterates evidence which renders the arguments behind these three claims as invalid, and, much more critically, irrelevant for our paper's key findings. Potentially more importantly, however, this paper goes on to build on a significant amount of common ground with Kincer et al.'s valuable contribution, suggesting how this useful discussion can be moved forward fruitfully, most notably relating to the key importance of driving sustainable development through adequate decision making in Africa's power sector.

Response to critique

(1) Alleged significant overestimation of coal capacity. In response to this claim, five points need to be considered. Firstly, the actual discrepancy between our coal prediction and Kincer et al.'s own assessment is significantly smaller than what Kincer et al. appear to suggest. A key difference in our and Kincer et al.'s assessment is that Kincer et al. do not count those coal plants which are under construction towards new coal capacity additions, but

¹ The EIA study uses a different, non-data-driven method to project generation shares of roughly 20% of non-hydro renewables and 63% fossil fuel in Africa in 2030, albeit with a higher coal share than our paper

instead consider them operational already. This is against the convention in the academic and grey energy planning literature. At the time of writing our paper, a large share of South Africa's large-scale Medupi and Kusile coal plants, as well as several other, smaller coal plants, were under construction but not yet partially or fully operational. These plants are therefore included in the predicted new coal additions in our paper. They alone account for roughly 10 GW of the 31 GW of our predicted coal capacity additions, but do not feature in Kincer et al.'s assessment². In addition, Kincer et al. find that roughly 1 GW coal capacity (in addition to plants under construction) is likely to come online, and a further 7 GW are in an early stage of development, implying a remaining discrepancy to our prediction of 13 – 20 GW. Furthermore, a quick database comparison appears to suggest some discrepancies, with the Global Energy Monitor (GEM) database Kincer et al. are using may be missing some coal projects which are listed in the Africa Energy database. Taking these points together, the remaining discrepancy is probably less than 15 GW, equating to only 22% of our total coal prediction across Africa in 2030, and limiting Kincer et al.'s entire critique to only 3% of our overall predicted capacity in the paper.

Secondly, Kincer et al. base their own assessment of whether or not coal capacity will come online on subjective and selective judgement. The GEM database used by Kincer et al. lists a substantial pipeline of yet-to-be-built coal-fired power plants totalling 88 GW in Africa. As of 2021, GEM lists roughly three quarters of this capacity as “shelved” or “cancelled”. To arrive at their coal capacity assessment, Kincer et al. do not scrutinise the entire GEM database, but simply manually downgrade the vast majority of projects classified in GEM as “announced”, “pre-permit” and “permitted” to being “effectively cancelled”, and consider all “shelved” or “cancelled” projects as failed. They neither provide any substantive evidence or objective criteria for why they downgraded the official GEM database status classifications where they did, nor for why they, by contrast, seem to trust GEM's status assessment of all those projects where GEM classified them as “shelved” or “cancelled”³. For our paper, we have abstained from manual editing power plant status definitions, instead using the assessments provided in the Africa Energy database throughout. Africa Energy is one of the most well-established and knowledgeable organisations in terms of African power sector asset data with over 30 years of experience of working in Africa's energy sector, building its asset-level assessments on the insights from local researchers in 44 different countries. In addition to avoid introducing subjective judgement, not altering their project-by-project status assessment is also key to ensure consistency across generation technologies and robustness of predicting relative generation shares.

Thirdly, it is critical to consider that our paper is based on an end-of-2018 data pull, with our paper stating in its abstract and throughout that our predictions are likely “unless a decarbonisation shock occurs”. Between the end of 2018 and 2021, there have been a number of signs of one such decarbonisation shock occurring, namely within the realm of international finance for coal projects. In June 2021, all G7 countries have committed to stop financing coal-

² While Kincer et al. cite a range of 31 – 36 GW of coal additions predicted in our *Nature Energy* paper, the correct number is 31 GW. This 31 GW number was communicated to Kincer et al. in a prior Email conversation. It is not stated in the *Nature Energy* paper (as it was not a focus of the analyses), but can be calculated directly from the information provided in the main text of the paper, using the total predicted failure rate of coal, the overall predicted failure rate, the share of coal in the pipeline and the total new additions. This yields 31 GW when non-rounded values are used.

³ It should be noted that browsing through those projects the GEM database classifies as “shelved” or “cancelled” suggests a lack of an unambiguous and consistently applied definition of when a project is classified as “shelved” or “cancelled”.

fired power plants abroad, and, perhaps more crucially for Africa, in September 2021 China has made a similar announcement. China is responsible for a large share of power sector investments in Africa, so these recent coal finance withdrawals are likely to reduce the realisation chances of considerable shares of the region's coal power plant pipeline going forward. This, however, does not constitute a methodological problem in our paper, but, by contrast, is covered explicitly in our paper in its section on decarbonisation shocks analyses which shows significantly lower coal shares in such scenarios.

Fourthly, even despite these points, Kincer et al.'s critique does not have the potential to affect our paper's main findings. Even in the theoretical case where no new coal outside of the coal plants already under construction end-of-2018 would come online across Africa, the resulting 2030 non-hydro renewables generation share would only increase from 9.6% (which we predict in our paper) to 10.1%. This thus would not affect the low likelihood of quick solar and wind transition scenarios coming true unless a decarbonisation shock occurs in the pipeline – if anything, it might reinforce this insight as a further, albeit only theoretical, robustness test⁴.

Finally, it should be noted that while Kincer et al. write that our study foresees a “boom” in new coal generation, our paper indeed predicts a substantial 30% decline of the coal capacity share in Africa. Kincer et al. state that the projections by the 2019 International Energy Agency (IEA) African Energy Outlook (IEA, 2019) are “far more plausible”. Yet in fact, our results agree closely with the IEA in predicting a decline of six percentage points of the coal capacity share in Africa between 2018 and 2030: Our study predicts a decrease from 21% to 15%, the IEA Stated Policies scenario predicts a decrease from 20% to 14%. Yet while Kincer et al. call the IEA result (14% coal share) “modest”, they equate our result (15% coal share) with a “coal-driven energy future for Africa”, an assessment which is inconsistent with our paper's results. The total coal capacity in 2030 in the IEA's Stated Policies scenario is slightly lower than ours (55 GW compared to our 68 GW), which, by design⁵, is due to the comparably low demand the IEA has assumed for 2030 (1284 TWh compared to the 1,600 – 2,150 TWh found in the extant literature). Increasing the assumed demand in the IEA study to one at the lower end of the spectrum used in the literature would yield almost exactly the same total installed coal capacity in Africa in 2030 as our paper predicted through its data-driven approach.

(2) Alleged analytical aggregation. Kincer et al.'s claim that our “analysis treats Africa as one unified entity” is false. Instead, our paper's machine learning-based analyses is, by definition, an empirically-driven, bottom-up approach which does not analytically aggregate African countries, or even power plants within African countries. Indeed, a key part of its novelty this degree of sub-national disaggregation our data-driven analysis achieves. Two recent comment papers in the leading academic journals *Joule* (Nock, 2021) and *Nature*

⁴ In a footnote, Kincer et al. label our 37 GW West Africa gas prediction as “aggressive”, saying that this was “at least five times the capacity of potential gas transactions being tracked by the US government's Power Africa initiative.” The Power Africa initiative only tracks projects financed by the US and its Power Africa partners. This does not include any state-owned generation projects (of which there are a substantial number for gas in Nigeria, for instance), finance from the EU, China and most Asian and Middle Eastern donors, and also does not include a substantial amount of private sector-financed projects. Indeed, the Power Africa database tracks less than one fifth of the capacity in the Africa Energy data, hence a substantial discrepancy between these two databases is not surprising.

⁵ The IEA projections are based on scenario modelling and not on pipeline data, hence their absolute values for installed capacities are by definition driven by the assumed demand.

Energy (McCollum, 2021) specifically applaud our “highly granular” approach (McCollum, 2021, p. 121) as a novel “solution for integrating local factors into energy planning” (Nock, 2021, p. 1031). Our paper features a total of 19 different country-specific variables, and 8 different project-level variables that capture the specific and time-dependent economic, social, existing energy mix and infrastructure-related as well as different political and governance context in all power plants and their respective country-years separately. This allows us to identify the key differentiating factors between assets and between countries, which in turn drive differences in power plant pipeline success chances. While we find asset-level variables to be significantly more critical for project success, we devote an entire section of the paper to analysing and visualising spatial disparities in our results, discussing regional and country-level differences in-depth, including context-specific insights for different fossil fuel technologies.

Furthermore, it is important to note that contrary to what Kincer et al. appear to suggest, our key finding of low non-hydro renewable shares applies to almost all countries in Africa individually: As of 2018, while some African countries rely heavily on hydroenergy, no country in Africa had a combined wind and solar generation share of more than 15%. By 2030, current pipeline data and our predictions suggest that the vast majority of African countries are likely to stay below 20%, implying a continued reliance on fossil fuels and/or hydroenergy, the latter being subject to increasing supply security risk potential due to rapidly increasing drought events in Africa. Critically, our results suggest that the shift to solar and wind in Africa is not going to happen automatically, but needs significantly increased effort if it is desired. In this regard, in agreement with Kincer et al.’s assessment that the South African case is special, we discuss it in more depth than any other country case in the paper. We predict South Africa to be an outlier in terms of its high pace of its transition to non-hydro renewables, with their combined solar and wind generation share increasing to markedly above 20% in 2030. While context-specific, we argue that there could be important lessons to learn from South Africa’s successful Renewable Energy Independent Power Producer Procurement Programme for scaling up the deployment of solar and wind in other African countries (Eberhard & Naude, 2016).

(3) Alleged call for a blanket ban on development finance for fossil fuels. Kincer et al.’s claim that “the authors of the Nature Energy article ... call for a continent-wide ban on development finance for all fossil fuels” is false. However, our study does not even mention blanket bans on fossil fuel finance. It presents and discusses an evidence-based finding that the extant leapfrog scenarios in the literature are unlikely “unless a rapid decarbonization shock occurs” (Alova et al., 2021, p. 158). In its discussion section, our paper provides an evidence-based and conditional statement, namely that if achieving a decisive low-carbon transition in accordance with projections in extant rapid decarbonisation scenarios is desired, then “besides promoting RE expansion, continued investment in fossil fuel plants should be disincentivized” (Alova et al., 2021, p. 161). Based on consulting the existing literature (Pfeiffer et al., 2018), we then list three “[c]ommon policy mechanisms to foster [disincentivising fossil fuel investment]”, one of which being “the exit of DFIs, both national and international, from fossil fuel projects”. Listing this project-level option for consideration has nothing to do with calling for a continent-wide blanket ban on development finance for fossil fuels. What we do find evidence for in the paper is that development finance increases the success chances of project realisation, an effect that is particularly salient for technologies with comparably low

success chances (such as wind) compared to technologies with high success chances (such as oil and gas). Hence, development finance appears to be more critical for some technologies, many of which comparably nascent non-hydro renewables, than others in terms of successfully realising them, implying that moving some of the DFI finance into renewables has a larger per-project effect of success chance increase on average than in fossil fuels. We believe this insight needs to be considered when allocating development finance to de-risk power sector investments and attract additional private finance, given the key role of DFI for growing nascent markets (see also (Steffen et al., 2018)).

Building on Kincer et al.: The need for development-driven energy planning

The sustainable development challenges associated with Africa's power sector are well-described in the literature. Insufficient funding has long been a key obstacle (Trotter et al., 2017), and Kincer et al. make a powerful case when urging more finance to be made available to support low-income and lower-middle income countries (LMICs) to meet their pressing energy needs. For instance, high-income countries have pledged to contribute 100 bn USD for climate financing in LMICs per year, a commitment that currently is not being honoured (OECD, 2020), and is very likely to be too small (Averchenkova et al., 2020).

There is a critical gap in the conceptual and analytical literature as to which generation technologies are best-suited to drive socio-economic development in Africa going forward (Nock, 2021). Indeed, Nock writes in *Joule* that "Alova et al. do not discuss whether or not a focus on fossil fuels is good or bad for different African countries from a short-term socio-economic development perspective, highlighting an area for future research" (Nock, 2021, p. 1032). Decarbonisation is a key objective of sustainable development, and all African countries have signed the Paris Agreement, implying, among other measures, a need to greatly ramp-up renewable energy-based generation and ultimately moving on from coal and gas-fired generation (with the latter feared of having a similar global warming potential compared to coal due to potentially very high methane leakages in the African gas industry (IEA, 2017)). At the same time, Kincer et al.'s notion of context-specificity, and their push to consider development at large when making energy-related decisions in African countries are highly important points and critical to consider. Recent contributions to this debate have not yet been fully able to provide conceptually sound, analytically balanced and evidence-based solutions to how to do so. Currently, the vast majority of African countries, individually and on aggregate, are likely to rely on fossil fuels and/or hydroenergy to meet a large majority of their electricity demand this decade (Alova et al., 2021). Nock identifies "multiple reasons why a fossil fuel-heavy approach might not be the best option", and goes on to say that "[w]hile I do not argue that a full fossil fuel fleet will by any means be good for the environment and electricity costs, I cannot deny the value of large-scale baseload generation that may aid in developing the manufacturing sector". Indeed, given the well-known fundamental role energy plays for development, energy planners have to answer the key question whether the current country-specific energy sector pathways reflected in their power plant pipeline are optimal for short-term and long-term socio-economic development. To answer this question, energy planning needs to start doing justice to the multi-objective nature of this issue by moving beyond its "supply meets demand" paradigm and becoming analytically significantly more integrated. Specifically, it needs to explicitly feature conjoint quantitative and qualitative analyses of the relevant context-specific economic, social, environmental, technical and institutional impact of coal, natural gas, hydro and non-hydro renewable power plants,

including key factors such costs, the generation technology-specific short-term versus long term differences in financial risks, projected finance availability, social and environmental impacts as well as climate change risks, job creation and wealth distribution opportunity, and related wider economic development opportunities.

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